

Analysis of Practical Goals of Learning a Foreign Language

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Abstract. *In this article, the goals of foreign language education have been widely discussed in methodological literature, the term applied methodology has caused more than one association among teachers, and opinions are given about concepts of different sizes and forms.*

Keywords: *second language teaching, general education, curriculum, linguistic information, linguistics, level of speech communication, simple rules.*

Introduction: Any goal arises out of necessity. The abbreviation "goal" means a planned result, an imagined result. To the question of why a foreign language is taught at school, the answer can be answered that they learn a foreign language for practical, educational, educational and developmental purposes. Educational goals are a social order - a task, and are focused on the formation and education of a well-developed individual. The goals of foreign language education have been widely discussed in methodological literature. By the second half of the sixties of the last century, the terms of practical, educational and educational goals were interpreted in accordance with the requirements of the time. In the 1980s, the term development goal appeared in addition to all three names. A deep analysis of this concept-term was carried out by professor G.Rogova, one of the prolific methodists. Thus, a foreign language is taught for four purposes.

The first - practical purpose - priority. The term "practical methodology" has caused more than one association among teachers and evokes concepts of different sizes and shapes. There are also misconceptions about the practice as 'speaking' or 'speaking'. There is also a correct general definition of the practical acquisition of a foreign language, understanding the speech of others and expressing one's opinion.

Material and methods: The ultimate goal of learning a foreign language in a practical way in the secondary education course is to get information by reading. Graduates of schools, lyceums and colleges, as a final goal, master the type of speech activity in a foreign language, such as reading. The intermediate goal is different. Speaking can be learned for intermediate purposes from the types of speech activities at the educational stage or in separate classes. E.g. in the initial period, they learn oral speech as a goal.

At the same time, reading and writing are also taught, but they are treated as tools. Now there is a need to define the conflict of terms - "goal" and "means". Since speech is a means of communication, learning it (speech is a set of types of speech activity) is part of the general practical goal of education. A type of speech activity represents a specific practical goal at the level of final or intermediate goal. E.g. speaking is studied in the first period of foreign language teaching as a private intermediate, leading practical purpose, and in the upper grades, reading takes over. In all classes, listening comprehension is studied with a special practical purpose. Writing as a type of speech activity is a tool for teaching a foreign language in all classes. The meaning of the term tool is "assistant in acquiring other types of speech activity". E.g. after the speaking or reading exercise, the language material they are learning is reinforced and repeated in writing. The term goal in foreign

language methodology can be explained as follows.

In order for the type of speech activity to receive the status of a goal, first of all, it must have its own educational content (speech topic, speech skills, language material), secondly, the language material must first be studied in this type of speech activity, and thirdly, time and the main part of the effort is spent, and finally, fourthly, most of the exercises must be done in this type of speech activity. E.g. speaking is taught on the basis of a special topic and language material in the first stage, and reading has exactly such a position in the upper grades. Speaking topics and lexical-grammatical material of the elementary period are repeated and strengthened in reading and writing.

The recommended methodological criteria are sufficient for the interpretation of the practical purpose. When teaching the type of speech activity, if the four methodological criteria are not observed, it will lose its goal level and take its place among educational tools. A foreign language article can be given as an example. The grammatical phenomenon of the article is studied in the following order in the types of speech activities: listening comprehension-» speaking-» writing-» reading.

The first and second of them (listening and speaking) are the specific goal of education, and the other two (writing and reading) are educational tools. An ancient question arises by itself: why is language material mastered in all types of speech activity? The problem is that the more the learner participates in the acquisition of any phenomenon in objective reality, including foreign language units, the stronger his dynamic stereotype will be.

Understanding the purpose of education helps to learn the general direction (strategy) of teaching. The goal is realized by completing many specific tasks during the lesson and independent work. Solving the problem is an educational tactic. Educational tasks consist of practical tasks performed by students (understanding, expressing thoughts, learning a language unit, etc.). Acquiring a foreign language (achieving a practical goal) serves as a basis and condition for solving educational and educational goals.

In short, learning a foreign language for practical purposes means getting the necessary information using this language and conveying it to others. The obtained information (information) serves to increase the level of knowledge of students (educational goal) and to educate the students. General educational goal of foreign language teaching. Students are taught a foreign language as a third language. A foreign language, which is one of the compulsory subjects, contributes to general education among other subjects. Both the result and the process of learning a foreign language are of general educational importance. Because in addition to the information obtained through the medium of a foreign language, language units used in the process of learning it develop thinking, new events in the expressive plan of speech are interesting for students and enrich their language experience. In the language material, students encounter events that do not correspond to their mother tongue. E.g. These include the complex form of the verb tense in grammar, polysemy (multiple meanings) in the lexicon, and phonetic units that are not found in the mother tongue or second language in pronunciation. Many linguistic phenomena are similar in different languages. Knowing the commonalities and differences between languages helps to increase the student's level of knowledge.

Students will be familiar with the culture, art, history, literature, customs and traditions of the country(s) where the language is being studied. They enjoy the cumulative function of the language as a treasure of national culture. Students will be lucky to "watch" their mother tongue (and second language) in the mirror of this language while taking the communicative function of the studied foreign language.

At the first stage of language learning, more attention is paid to mastering lexical, grammatical and pronunciation units in the process of oral speech. At a higher level, collecting information from foreign language graphics and audio text increases students' desire to learn about vital news.

So, when a school student learns a foreign language for general educational purposes, he gets educational information of two different contents. The first type of information consists of rules,

concepts and information about specific phenomena of the language that explain the material of the studied foreign language (lexical, grammatical and pronunciation). A simple knowledge of a language is completely different from a deep theoretical system. Foreign language teaching should not be theorized. It is a methodological principle that a simple theory is sufficient only for the formation of speech skills. We should not forget the methodical motto "we teach speech in a foreign language" (not the sum of knowledge about a foreign language) recognized in scientific literature and recognized by teachers.

Result and discussion: In the teaching of the mother tongue and the second language, the general educational information about them is absorbed in a larger volume than in the foreign language. After all, the teaching of the first and second languages takes place in natural conditions, and the number of lesson hours allocated to them in the curriculum is much larger. Accordingly, theoretical and linguistic information of general educational importance can be easily studied in the mother tongue and the second language. It is appropriate to compare the ratio of knowledge of linguistics in language teaching with the following life picture. The bigger the city, the better the drivers need to know the rules of the road. E.g. Cities such as New York, Tokyo, Seoul, Moscow, London are overpopulated and dense, and so are the number of cars and pedestrians on the streets. So, the traffic manager and pedestrians need to keep in mind a large number of street traffic and other information. Or in the cities of Tashkent, Kabul, Tbilisi, a driver with less knowledge than the above can manage the transport. In rural areas or small towns, the traffic manager may have even less information.

The rules of "management" of the language are similar to this example, that is, theoretical knowledge in the native language is the maximum amount, in an average environment - the basics of linguistics are reduced in the second language, and in the limited conditions of the foreign language, the minimum amount of simple theory, that is, simple it is recommended to know the training rules. Despite the limited volume of foreign language educational material, work is carried out in accordance with the created conditions.

Conclusion: Learning a foreign language for educational purposes is useful for developing the student's logical thinking, improving memory, and raising their level of knowledge and general culture. By learning a foreign language, students learn language phenomena as real facts in speech. By learning a foreign language at the level of speech communication, the student will understand its content plan on the basis of language tools (plan of expression). So, there are three objects of general education: language phenomena, concepts and rules, and speech (text) content. I have certain sizes and measurements. Conducting speech activities, as a result, exchanging information, is the only multifaceted goal of teaching a foreign language subject. But the material used in the speech itself is the knowledge that turns into a skill, and the knowledge in the form of abstractions formed from it is a set of simple rules (abstractions). In a word, knowing the rules, language units and content of texts is general education in a foreign language. General education is realized during the practical knowledge of a foreign language. Practical knowledge is the main way to educate.

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